

COMPOSITE MICROPOWDERS FOR ADDITIVE PRODUCTION METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The technology of obtaining composite micropowders, allowing the production of a wide range of composite powders suitable for use in additive technologies, is proposed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the additive technologies (SLS/SLM, EBM, DMD) are used in high-tech industries, such as medical industry [1, 2], machine manufacturing [1, 3-6], aerospace industry [1, 7]. Further development of additive technologies involves the range expansion of materials used. One of the most promising directions is the creation of products from composite materials [8-11].

Composite materials manufactured by additive methods can be conditionally divided into 3 groups: metal [12-15], ceramic [16, 17], and those based on materials of different nature [18-27].

It is noteworthy that not only the composition but also the production processes for these composites formulation might be significantly different. For instance, the synthesis of titanium nitride from titanium powder exposed to laser radiation in an atmosphere of gaseous nitrogen is considered in the papers [28-30]. The papers [31, 32] discuss the formation of intermetallic phases at furnace annealing of the structures obtained by the SLS method from bimetallic powder compositions. The properties of the samples made from different powder compositions (nickel, brass, bronze) by the SLS method were studied in the paper [33]. The impact of nickel-titanium powder compositions and fritting conditions on the phase composition of fritted structures is under consideration in the papers [34-36].

Important characteristics of micropowders that determine the quality of the resulting products are flow rate of powder and bulk density. The values of flow rate of powder and bulk density depend on the powder particle shape. Typically, the powders with spherical particles are used in additive technologies.

The aim of the present work is to develop a production method for composite micropowders, which are suitable in additive technology applications.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed method consists of two steps:

- obtaining metal micropowders by atomization of the molten metal in the gas jet;
- modification of the surface of the obtained micropowders as a result of the mechanochemical synthesis.

Molten metal (copper) atomization is performed using the URM-001 apparatus (Figure 1) [37]. Melting the metal and a subsequent superheat of the liquid melt at 200-250 °C above the melting temperature were performed using the induction melting furnace 1; further, as a result of excessive pressure in the sealed cavity of the induction furnace, the molten metal is supplied through the feed pipe 2 to the central aperture of the spray nozzle 3.

Figure 1: Molten metal atomization apparatus: 1 – induction furnace, 2 – molten metal feed pipe, 3 – spray nozzle, 4 – collection storage hopper.

The molten metal jet contacts with the gas jet, which results in atomization of the melt (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The process of metal atomization in the molten metal atomization apparatus URM-001.

Metal powders obtained in the first stage are characterized by an average particle size of about 50 micron [38] with the spherical shape of particles [39].

The mixture of collected copper powder and nanopowder of carbon black were used in the mechanochemical synthesis. The particle of the resulting composite micropowder is a metal sphere (Figure 3), most of which is covered with carbon black nanopowder.

Figure 3: Photograph of copper powder taken by the scanning microscope JSM-6400LV: a – before modification, b – after modification.

The presence of an untreated surface of the particle is necessary to improve the process of subsequent fritting/alloying of the particles.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the main requirements to the powders used in additive technologies is the shape of the particles. High flow rates and bulk density might be achieved with the spherical shape of particles. To estimate the shape of composite powder particles the method of optical analysis was chosen. The comparison of the shape of resulting composite powder particles (Figure 4) with the shape of the particles of the Steel Powder H13 that is used in additive technologies (Figure 5) was performed with the optical analyzer OCCHIO 500 nano.

Figure 4: Results of the particle shape study (Width/Length) for the composite powder using the optical analyzer OCCHIO 500 nano.

Figure 5: Results of the particle shape study (Width/Length) for the Steel Powder H13 using the optical analyzer OCCHIO 500 nano.

According to the analysis results, we might conclude that the sphericity of particles of the produced composite powder is not inferior to the sphericity of particles of the Steel Powder H13 that is used in additive technologies.

Figure 6: Results of the particle shape study (Mean Diameter/ISO Roundness) for the composite powder using the optical analyzer OCCHIO 500 nano.

Figure 7: Results of the particle shape study (Mean Diameter/ISO Roundness) for the Steel Powder H13 using the optical analyzer OCCHIO 500 nano.

The results of particle roundness studies (Figures 6 and 7) indicate a large proportion of rounded particles in the total weight of the composite powder.

4 CONCLUSION

The production method for composite micropowders, which are suitable in additive technology applications, is developed. The proposed method consists of two steps: obtaining metal micropowders by atomization of the molten metal in the gas jet; and modification of the surface of the obtained micropowders as a result of the mechanochemical synthesis. The shape of the resulting composite powder particles is nearly spherical. The presence of fragments, which are free of graphite, on the surface of the composite material suggests the best conditions of fritting/alloying of the powder. The proposed composition is recommended for the fabrication of current collector elements [40]; while the developed method enables to manufacture a wide range of compositions in additive technology applications.

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